

SOME ISSUES OF ANALYSIS OF CAPITAL IN COMMERCIAL ENTERPRISES

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*PhD in economics,**docent of the Accounting and Audit Department of Azerbaijan University of Cooperation Baku, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

The article shows the economic nature of the capital of a commercial enterprise and talks about a number of issues of capital analysis based on it. Here, the purpose, tasks and information sources of the capital analysis are indicated, and the use of the share ratio of capital in total assets (SRCTA) indicator in the analysis is justified. In addition, some issues of the analysis of the authorized capital, shareholder capital and retained earnings, which are the main components of capital, are explained.

Keywords: assets, capital, SRCTA indicator, retained earnings, financial stability of the enterprise.

Introduction. It is known that the capital of the enterprise is a balance indicator reflecting the amount of its own funds. What is the total amount of capital, in which cases is this amount considered optimal, and in which cases is it considered sub-optimal, or what is the position of the relative indicators reflecting the current state of capital in the financial situation of the enterprise, among the issues that are considered relevant in the economic field, it attracts the attention of researchers. is involved. One of the convenient measures to determine whether the total amount of capital is sufficient for the enterprise is to periodically and regularly analyze the capital. The final provisions obtained as a result of the analysis make it necessary to make management decisions on maintaining the physical volume of capital, whether it is sufficient or not, and whether it should be increased in the future activity of the enterprise.

Capital appreciation. A number of indicators are used to characterize the financial condition of a commercial enterprise. As the scale of such indicators has a wide scope, they are used both in financial analysis and in the organization of management processes, as well as in making management decisions. In addition to these, the indicator of the share ratio of capital in its total assets can form a sufficiently justified opinion in order to briefly and clearly characterize the financial situation of any commercial enterprise. A greater amount of capital results in a higher share of capital in the total assets of the enterprise. In addition, the condition of the components of the capital plays an influential role with various factors in the assessment of the financial condition of the enterprise. All this makes it necessary to regularly analyze the capital and form reasonable opinions about the financial situation of the enterprise through it. Some issues of capital analysis in commercial enterprises have been investigated in the works of a number of economists [4, 14, 15, 16]. Despite this, the capital valuation issues to be commented on here have not been sufficiently investigated.

The main purpose of capital analysis is to make scientifically based judgments about the financial condition and financial stability of the enterprise, and thus help to find directions for the efficient development of the economy of the enterprise. In order to achieve this goal in a favorable way, analysis should be carried out in several directions. First, it is

considered appropriate to analyze the total volume of the enterprise's capital, and then its composition and structure. Each of these can be analyzed in different ways, but the judgments formed on the results of the analysis are equally important in directing the development of the enterprise.

Sources of information and tasks of analysis.

What information is used in the process of capital analysis may be different depending on the purpose of the analysis and the requirements set before it. To analyze the availability of capital, the current state of its composition and how it changes over the years, it is enough to use the information reflected in the financial statements of the enterprise. However, in order to analyze how the enterprise's capital was historically formed, its development, for what purposes and how it is used in the process of the enterprise's activity, and a number of other such delicate issues, it is necessary to look at information stored in deeper layers, archival materials of the past years, founding documents of the enterprise, distribution of profits over the years and it is required to refer to usage protocols and other such information [1, 3, 5].

The main sources of information for the analysis of capital in general and at the initial stage are the following forms of the financial report of the enterprise:

1. Report on the financial situation: it is a form of financial report that reflects the financial situation of the enterprise in a comparative form. In the "Capital" section of this report, the balance amounts for individual components of the capital of the enterprise are reflected.

2. Statement of changes in capital: it is one of the forms of financial statement reflecting the movement of the private capital of the enterprise. The components of special capital include authorized capital, reserve capital, additional capital, as well as undistributed profits of the reporting year and previous years.

Different kinds of tasks can be put before the analysis of capital. As an example, it is appropriate to show the following:

- ✓ to determine the sources of capital formation, to determine the results of changes in its total volume and composition;
- ✓ to determine the ability of the enterprise to use the capital effectively;
- ✓ evaluate capital increase reserves;

✓ to evaluate the parts of the undistributed profit of the enterprise related to the current year and collected from previous years and other similar tasks.

Analysis process and SRCTA indicator. It is appropriate to start the process of analyzing the capital of the enterprise by collecting, examining, interpreting and presenting information about the current state of its existence and how it has changed over the past few years. Financial statements from the last few years are required to perform these processes. First of all, the dynamic change and development trends of the capital over the years, and then the changes in its composition are analyzed. In modern times, the economic literature provides information about a number of relative indicators that reflect these or other issues of the enterprise's capital [9, 10, 18]. In our opinion, it is appropriate to use another relative indicator here. This

indicator is called the share ratio of capital in the total assets of the enterprise (SRCTA). It expresses the ratio of the enterprise's capital to total assets. This indicator can create a preliminary idea that the enterprise has sufficient capital. Thus, the SRCTA indicator can play an important role in assessing the financial condition and financial stability of the enterprise. Here, using SOCAR's financial reports as an example, let's take a brief look at some of the issues of calculating and using the equity ratio in the total assets and using it in the analysis.

Using the information contained in SOCAR's 2018-2022 reports on the financial situation, the following table shows how to calculate the share ratio of capital in the total assets of the company (SRCTA indicator).

Table

Share ratio of capital in total assets of SOCAR
(according to indicators at the end of the year)

(mln.\$)

№	Years	Total assets, mln \$	Total capital, mln \$	SRCTA indicator, %
1.	2018	36550,6	14084,7	38,53
2.	2019	38455,9	14310,6	37,21
3.	2020	37738,2	12895,9	34,17
4.	2021	40798,2	13382,4	32,80
5.	2022	47550,0	19608,8	41,24

Source: compiled by the author based on SOCAR's Consolidated financial statements [1]

To calculate the SRCTA indicator, you need to multiply the amount of the company's total capital by 100 and divide it by the amount of total assets. This indicator can give a reasonable idea about the financial situation of the enterprise. Here, the process of calculating the SRCTA indicators of SOCAR at the end of the respective years was carried out as follows:

By the end of 2018: $14084.7 \times 100 : 36550.6 = 38.53\%$;

By the end of 2019: $14310.6 \times 100 : 38455.9 = 37.21\%$;

By the end of 2020: $12895.9 \times 100 : 37738.2 = 34.17\%$;

By the end of 2021: $13382.4 \times 100 : 40798.2 = 32.80\%$;

By the end of 2022: $19608.8 \times 100 : 47550.0 = 41.24\%$.

As can be seen from the information reflected in the table, serious changes have occurred in the total amount of assets and capital of SOCAR in 2018-2022. Thus, in the specified 5 years, the total amount of the company's assets increased by \$10,999.4 million, or 30.1 percent, and the total amount of its capital increased by \$5,524.1 million, or 39.2 percent. The amount of both assets and capital has changed unevenly over the years, sometimes increasing and sometimes

decreasing. Here, the decline in 2020 attracts more attention. In that year, the company's assets decreased by \$717.6 million, and its capital decreased by \$1414.7 million. The company ended the year 2020, when the pandemic prevailed all over the world, with a loss of \$1,155.9 million, as a result of which the amount of its total capital decreased by \$1,414.7 million. Although the situation has improved slightly in the next year 2021, the total amount of capital has still not reached the level of 2019. In 2021, the capital increased by \$486.5 million compared to the previous year, which was not enough to reach the level of 2019. A significant increase in the company's assets and capital took place in 2022, which is related to the improvement of its management system. As can be seen from the presented information, in 2022, compared to the previous year, the amount of assets increased by \$6,910.6 million, and the amount of capital increased by \$6,226.5 million, which is the highest indicator in the analyzed five-year period. How the company's total assets and capital have changed is reflected in the next diagram (Diagram).

Diagram

Source: Compiled by the author based on table information

As reflected in the chart given here, in 2018, 2019, 2021 and 2022, when the company's assets increased, its capital also increased, and in 2020, when it decreased, its capital also decreased. Undoubtedly, there is a hidden connection between these two indicators, which is not easy to see, and its investigation will be the subject of another study. Here, we consider it appropriate to focus on the SRCTA indicator. This indicator is reflected in the last column of the above table. As can be seen, the value of the SRCTA indicator expressed as a percentage gradually decreased in 2019, 2020 and 2021, from 38.53% in 2018 to 32.80% at the

end of 2021, 3 5.73% decrease occurred during the year. In our opinion, this means that the company has blown money over the years, and the rapid growth of its assets has not resulted in a corresponding increase in capital. Such a negative situation was eliminated only in 2020. At the end of that year, the SRCTA indicator increased by 8.44% compared to the previous year and reached 41.24%. How the company's SRCTA indicator changes over the years is reflected in the following graph (Graph).

Graph

Source: Compiled by the author based on table information

As can be seen from the given graph, the SRCTA indicator of the company has tended to decrease regularly from year to year in 2018-2021, and only in 2022 it increased and rose above the level of 2018.

In our opinion, the indicator of 2022 reflecting the share ratio of capital in total assets in SOCAR can be considered very favorable and high for a commercial production organization. This ratio shows that 41.24% of the company's total assets are its own funds, and the remaining 58.76% are borrowed funds. In general, we consider it reasonable to accept the SRCTA indicator above 33.3% as a guarantor of the strength of the financial stability of the enterprise for this type of commercial enterprises. This indicator reflects that the total capital of the enterprise is more than 1/3 of the amount of its total assets.

Features of the analysis of capital components.

One of the important directions of capital analysis is the examination of its constituent parts. When analyzing the composition and structure of capital, it is necessary to take into account the characteristics of each part of it. When analyzing the composition and structure of the capital, it is appropriate to pay special attention to the authorized capital of the enterprise. The charter capital consists of the amount of funds that the founders invested in its property during the establishment of the enterprise. In Western literature, this type of capital is called nominal capital [7, 8, 19]. The authorized capital can be reorganized, increased or decreased during the operation of the enterprise. Necessary information about its volume (amount) and how it is organized is reflected in the founding documents of the enterprise [21; p. 330]. The most important of these documents is the charter of the enterprise. The status of the authorized capital during the reporting period is reflected in the report on the financial status of the enterprise, and its increase or decrease is reflected in the report on changes in capital. When analyzing the authorized capital, first of all, the completeness of its formation is evaluated, if necessary, it is determined which of the founders has not fulfilled their obligations to invest in the authorized capital. Then, the cases of its increase and decrease in the period covered by the analysis are examined, and the reasons, sources, directions and results of the changes are interpreted [2, 22].

In enterprises and organizations with the organizational form of a joint-stock company, the authorized capital is formed in the form of share capital. When analyzing shareholder capital, it is necessary to determine whether the organization has its own shares purchased from shareholders and the purpose of their purchase. The peculiarity of share capital is that through it many legal and natural persons invest in the enterprise on a long-term basis and they become the main legal owners of the enterprise through equity instruments [12, 17]. The social context of high share capital is that the shareholders of the enterprise are a part of the people in general, and thus it is known that the enterprise belongs to the people in the form of shareholders. The higher the share of publicly traded shares in the country, the more people-owned the economy is. Therefore, it is considered appropriate to

consider the share of the share capital in the total capital of the enterprises existing in the country or region as one of the indicators reflecting the extent to which the economy belongs to the people.

One of the parts of capital that should be paid special attention to is retained earnings. Retained earnings consist of the total amount of the unpaid parts of the net profit in the form of dividends earned by the enterprise in the process of long-term financial and economic activity [13,20]. These parts of the profit over the years remain accumulated and are added to the capital of the legal owners of the enterprise. When analyzing retained earnings, it is necessary to evaluate the change in its share in the total amount of capital. A decrease in this indicator may indicate a decrease in business activity and therefore should be the focus of the analyst's attention.

The result. Thus, capital analysis plays an important role in forming a correct picture of the company's financial situation. In the analysis of the capital, it is proposed to use the capital share ratio (SRCTA) indicator in the total assets, and the method of calculating this indicator is shown. Also, it is proposed to consider the share of shareholder capital in the total capital of enterprises existing in the country or region as one of the indicators reflecting the extent to which the economy belongs to the people.

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